

Supplementary Material: Heuristic Workflow Redesign Through a Sustainability Lens

Table 1: Workflow Redesign Heuristics Impact on Devil’s Pentagon Dimensions.

#	Heuristic	Quality	Time	Flexibility	Cost	Sustainability
Customer						
1.1	Control Relocation	↗	=	=	↗	↗
1.2	Contact Reduction	↗	↘	=	↗	↗
1.3	Integration	=	↘	↘	↘	↗
Business Process Operation						
2.1	Order Types	↘	↘	↘	↘	↗
2.2	Task Elimination	↘	↘	=	↘	↗
2.3	Order-based Work	=	↘	=	↗	↘
2.4	Triage	↗	↘	↘	↘	↗
2.5	Task Composition	↗	↘	↘	↘	↗
Business Process Behaviour						
3.1	Resequencing	=	↘	=	↘	↗
3.2	Knock-out	=	↗	=	↘	↗
3.3	Parallelism	↘	↘	↘	↗	↘
3.4	Exception	↗	↘	↘	=	=
Organization						
4.1	Order Assignment	↗	↘	↘	=	↗
4.2	Flexible Assignment	↗	↘	↘	=	↗
4.3	Centralization	=	↘	↗	↗	↗
4.4	Split Responsibilities	↗	=	↘	=	↗
4.5	Customer Teams	↗	↗	↘	=	↗
4.6	Numerical Involvement	↗	=	=	↗	↗
4.7	Case Manager	↗	=	=	↗	↗
4.8	Extra Resources	=	↘	↗	↗	↘
4.9	Specialist-Generalist	↗	=	↘	=	↗
4.10	Empower	↘	↘	=	↘	↗
Information						
5.1	Control Addition	↗	↗	=	↘	=
5.2	Buffering	=	↘	=	↗	↗
Technology						
6.1	Task Automation	↗	↘	↘	↘	↘
6.2	Integral Technology	=	↘	=	↗	↗
External Environment						
7.1	Trusted Party	=	↘	↘	↘	↗
7.2	Outsourcing	↘	=	↘	↘	↗
7.3	Interfacing	↗	↘	=	↘	↗

Note: Arrows denote change direction rather than desirability.

1 Customer

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Customer heuristics. Figure 1 shows the Devil's Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 1: Devil's Pentagon for Customer Heuristics

1.1 Control Relocation

This heuristic propose to 'move controls towards the customer' instead of applying such controls within the organization's business process. Its main consequence is a considerable improvement in the external quality of the process by increasing customer satisfaction. Shifting the responsibility for controls and checks in certain tasks to the customer can have a favorable impact in time and costs by reducing the number of activities involved in the process. However, this improvement may negatively affect costs due to issues such as an increase in the probability of fraud.

1.1.1 Sustainability Impact

The impact of reducing tasks in the process is even more positive when these tasks require significant computational or energy resources. It can also have a positive effect for the organization in scenarios where the controls that are no longer performed involve the use of materials such as paper, printed documents, or other physical resources.

1.1.2 Control Relocation Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, this practice should be prioritized for tasks whose control activities have a high environmental impact and could potentially be avoided. In cases where such controls remain necessary, relocating them may still have a positive effect if their independent execution by each customer results in a lower environmental impact than performing them centrally within the organization.

However, by moving these controls outside the organization, the organization loses part of its ability to monitor and measure their effects. As a result, although the impact within the organization may decrease, the problem could still persist or even worsen when considered from a broader, system-wide perspective.

1.2 Contact Reduction

This practice aims to “reduce the number of contacts with customers and third parties” and, in particular, to reduce information exchanges, whether physical or digital, as these typically involve additional time consumption. However, it may also increase the likelihood of introducing errors and generate additional activities, such as reconciliation tasks.

1.2.1 Sustainability Impact

Reducing contacts and information exchanges with customers may imply an improvement in terms of sustainability by reducing the impact associated with these tasks, particularly if they are carried out physically. On the other hand, reducing these information exchanges could lead to an increase in rework, waste generation, or coordination problems that may negatively affect sustainability.

1.2.2 Contact reduction Through a Sustainability Lens

This practice would focus on reducing contacts that have a greater sustainability impact, for example, those carried out physically in order to avoid transportation, or those involving material consumption, such as paper use or waste generation.

1.3 Integration

Integration proposes to “consider the integration with a business process of the customer or a supplier.” For example, in situations where two parties must work jointly to produce a result, performing coordinated intermediate checks can optimize the process compared to scenarios in which such checks are absent or carried out only sporadically. This practice may have a positive impact on time and cost, although it also creates a greater dependency between the parties involved.

1.3.1 Sustainability Impact

Integrating processes may have a negative impact on sustainability due to the increase in information exchange tasks and the associated process times. However, these information exchanges could be considered favorable in scenarios where they help reduce rework or the repetition of tasks among different actors.

1.3.2 Integration Through a Sustainability Lens

This best practice could be considered in cases where integration with external business processes is possible and these processes are more sustainable than the organization's own processes, or when they share the objective of performing tasks more efficiently. It may also imply the optimization of resource and material usage, thereby reducing consumption and waste. On the other hand, the interdependence generated and the delegation of responsibilities may also represent a loss of control over the sustainability of the external process and create the need for a higher level of integration and information exchange between systems.

2 Business Process Operation

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Business Process Operation heuristics. Figure 2 shows the Devil's Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 2: Devil's pentagon for Business Process Operation heuristics

2.1 Order types

This practice proposes to “determine whether tasks are related to the same type of order and, if necessary, distinguish new business processes,” which can improve process efficiency by creating subprocesses that can be reused. On the other hand, it may lead to a loss of quality by increasing coordination issues between processes and reducing flexibility.

2.1.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice can generate process optimizations by identifying and managing common subflows that are shared across multiple business processes. From a sustainability perspective, this can be positive, but there may also be cases where subdividing the process generates greater energy requirements, emissions, or resource consumption.

2.1.2 Order types Through a Sustainability Lens

Identifying, grouping, and relating tasks from a sustainability perspective can help mitigate the sustainability impact by efficiently handling these related tasks in the same way for all processes including them. In this way, it can help minimize aspects such as energy consumption and emissions. In addition, creating new specific business subprocesses with sustainability objectives can support reuse and optimization, for example by reducing raw material consumption and

waste. If the subprocess is implemented only once and invoked by all the processes that require it, infrastructure utilization and maintainability can be improved.

2.2 Task elimination

This practice seeks to ‘eliminate unnecessary tasks from a business process’, which may lead to improvements in execution times and costs. On the other hand, eliminating tasks from the process may also negatively affect the quality of the resulting products and services.

2.2.1 Sustainability Impact

Similar to what was mentioned in the Control Relocation heuristic, eliminating tasks from a process can have a positive impact in terms of sustainability, as it avoids the consumption of resources and the environmental effects associated with their execution. However, it should be considered that the eliminated tasks may be taken over by external actors, which would imply a transfer of the impact rather than an effective reduction of it. In Figure 2b the sustainability impact analysis on the Devil’s Pentagon is presented extended from [1], maintaining the original evaluation on the rest of the dimensions.

2.2.2 Task elimination Through a Sustainability Lens

The tasks to be eliminated should be those with the highest environmental impact that could potentially be avoided by implementing controls, process optimizations in previous tasks, or by prioritizing the most sustainable process variants. Redundant tasks should also be considered, as their individual impact may not be very high, but when considering the redundancy, they could represent a significant issue. As mentioned before the effect of no longer performing the task should also be taken into account. For example, if an organization stops delivering its products to customers, the impact associated with transportation, such as CO₂ emissions, is reduced. However, if each customer must travel to get the products, considering a broader scope, the problem still exists or gets even worse; it simply ceases to be a direct problem for the organization.

2.3 Order-based work

This heuristic consists of “consider removing batch-processing and periodic activities from a business process” with the aim of improving the speed of individual process instances by eliminating their dependence on periodic activities or on the availability of systems at specific points in time.

2.3.1 Sustainability Impact

Eliminating batch or periodic processing may be counterproductive from a sustainability perspective, as it can affect the optimization of resource and material

usage, waste generation, and emissions. This may require systems to be permanently available and prevent the use of resources that could otherwise be managed based on demand, workload, and potentially impact.

2.3.2 Order-based work Through a Sustainability Lens

This will be applied to batch or periodic processing that has a great impact on sustainability, such as energy consumption and associated CO₂ emissions, especially when the supporting infrastructure is not fully optimized. Splitting the work could also have an impact on the information systems that support it.

2.4 Triage

The most common interpretation of triage is to “consider the division of a general task into two or more alternative tasks” in order to better align tasks with resource capabilities. Another possible interpretation is to “consider the integration of two or more alternative tasks into one general task.” Both variants aim to improve process quality and resource utilization, potentially reducing time and cost, although excessive specialization may reduce process flexibility.

2.4.1 Sustainability Impact

Dividing general tasks into two or more alternative tasks may require additional resources for the execution and coordination of the different tasks, as well as greater software support to manage the different process paths. As a consequence, it could generate an increase in energy consumption and in the resources associated with process operation.

On the other hand, integrating two or more alternative tasks into a more general task may reduce operational complexity, decrease coordination requirements, and simplify the required technological support. As a result, it could contribute to a reduction in resource consumption and in the impact associated with process execution.

2.4.2 Triage Through a Sustainability Lens

The decision to divide or integrate tasks should consider not only traditional performance criteria, but also the environmental impact associated with each alternative. Task division should be prioritized when it allows the process to be adapted in order to avoid unnecessary activities or activities with a high environmental impact for certain types of cases. Similarly, task integration may be beneficial when it reduces redundancies and resource usage.

2.5 Task composition

Task composition consists of “combining small tasks into composite tasks and dividing large tasks into workable smaller tasks,” and can therefore be related to the triage heuristic. However, unlike triage, which aims to assign different

types of cases to specific tasks or resources, task composition seeks to integrate multiple tasks into a single one or divide overly complex tasks, with the goal of simplifying the process and reducing coordination time.

2.5.1 Sustainability Impact

Task composition may have a positive impact on sustainability when several small tasks are integrated into a single one, as it reduces setup times, coordination needs, and information exchanges between actors or systems. This can decrease resource consumption and the software usage associated with process execution. On the other hand, dividing tasks into smaller activities may increase these requirements by generating more coordination and work handoff points.

2.5.2 Task composition Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, the challenge is to find a balance between operational efficiency and environmental impact, avoiding both excessive fragmentation and overly complex tasks that ultimately increase resource consumption. As in the triage heuristic, the decision on whether to divide or compose tasks should be based on those tasks that have a negative impact in sustainability, such as energy consumption, waste generation.

3 Business Process Behaviour

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Business Process Behaviour heuristics. Figure 3 shows the Devil’s Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 3: Devil’s pentagon for Business Process Behaviour heuristics

3.1 Resequencing

This practice proposes to “move tasks to more appropriate places” with the aim of optimizing processes through task reordering. This can reduce costs by executing similar activities at nearby points in time, thereby reducing setup times and improving process efficiency.

3.1.1 Sustainability Impact

The impact on sustainability would depend on the type of tasks that are moved and their specific environmental impact, which could have a positive effect from the perspective of resource optimization and waste reduction.

3.1.2 Resequencing Through a Sustainability Lens

Task resequencing from a sustainability perspective can be applied in scenarios where a task can be postponed or advanced with the objective of minimizing the impact associated. For example, it can be used to reduce and optimize infrastructure usage during peaks and periods of low demand, directly reducing the operational emissions associated with data processing. This adjustment also makes it possible to avoid waste, potentially by grouping tasks that require the same type of materials. A concrete example is shifting heavy analytical processes or AI model training to periods with greater availability of renewable energy in order to take advantage of idle capacity and a cleaner electricity grid.

3.2 Knock-out

This best practice proposes to ‘order knock-outs in a decreasing order of effort and in an increasing order of termination probability’, to avoid doing unnecessary tasks. In this way, an improvement in costs is achieved, as process termination is accelerated through the reordering of tasks. This practice aims to bring forward the termination of process executions, which implies that fewer tasks are executed thus also reducing process time. However, the overall throughput time could eventually increase if the checking tasks could have been executed in parallel in the redesigned process.

3.2.1 Sustainability Impact

For the sustainability impact, it prevents the generation of emissions, energy consumption, the use of materials, and the generation of waste associated with the subsequent tasks in the process flow that will not be performed.

3.2.2 Knock-out Through a Sustainability Lens

This pattern could be applied by considering the sustainability impact when reordering controls. The original practice suggests prioritizing the controls that present a better ratio between the expected knock-out probability and the expected effort required to verify that condition. From a sustainability perspective, controls should be prioritized to maximize the ratio between the expected knock-out probability and the impact associated with the tasks that would be avoided. For example, if the process variants with the highest impact are identified, controls could be implemented to evaluate the probability of termination early in those cases.

3.3 Parallelism

This practice proposes executing tasks in parallel whenever possible in order to significantly reduce the process throughput time. As a drawback, it may require increased coordination and management of concurrent tasks, which could negatively affect process quality and flexibility.

3.3.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice may be inconvenient from a sustainability perspective in cases where it implies an increase in energy requirements and emissions. Parallel tasks make it more difficult to optimize the use of materials and may generate a higher level of waste. It could also imply the need for additional resources.

3.3.2 Parallelism Through a Sustainability Lens

This pattern applies to sustainability when reducing cycle time allows infrastructure usage to be optimized, but it must be managed carefully to avoid

resource waste. Tasks to perform in parallel should be selected based on their sustainability impact such as shared dependency on energy-intensive resources allowing infrastructure usage to be optimized.

3.4 Exception

This best practice aims to explicitly handle typical orders while isolating exceptional cases from the normal process flow and providing them with differentiated treatment. In this way, the execution of normal operations can be optimized. However, this practice may increase process complexity and reduce flexibility.

3.4.1 Sustainability Impact

Explicit exception handling may have opposing effects on sustainability. On the one hand, the incorporation of specialized tasks, controls, and resources to manage exceptions may increase resource consumption. On the other hand, by preventing exceptions from affecting the normal execution of standard cases, it may reduce rework, as well as potential waste generation and energy consumption caused by delays and process disruption.

3.4.2 Exception Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, this practice is particularly relevant when exceptions may generate environmental impacts that are significantly different from those of normal cases. In these scenarios, identifying and isolating exceptions makes it possible to apply specific mechanisms to mitigate such impacts.

For example, a distribution process may perform consolidated daily shipments with the objective of minimizing transport-related emissions. However, an exception may require the urgent and individual shipment of a product. If these situations are explicitly identified as exceptions, the process could incorporate alternative mechanisms, such as the use of transportation methods with a lower environmental impact.

4 Organization

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Organization heuristics. Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows the Devil's Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 4: Devil's pentagon for Organization Structure

Figure 5: Devil's pentagon for Organization Population

4.1 Order assignment

This practice aims to improve service quality and reduce setup times by “letting workers perform as many steps as possible for single orders.” As a drawback, it may reduce flexibility in resource allocation. Furthermore, waiting times may increase when the responsible resource is not available.

4.1.1 Sustainability Impact

The sustainability impact could be beneficial since the need to print documents or using materials or systems from different workers are minimized, as well as

errors and associated rework. Also for physical tasks the emissions and waste can be reduced.

4.1.2 Order assignment Through a Sustainability Lens

The sustainability focus will be on assigning tasks that share the same digital or physical supplies, e.g., minimizing transportation needs, or system setup. When the process has high negative impact due to communication errors within people from different units, the same worker can keep sustainability objectives in mind, thus avoiding rework and minimizing waste.

4.2 Flexible assignment

By “assigning resources in such a way that maximal flexibility is preserved for the near future,” this practice aims to reduce the overall queue time by avoiding dependence on specific resources. If the most specialized available resources are assigned at any given time, process quality may also be improved. However, this flexibility may lead to variations in outcomes due to differences among the assigned resources.

4.2.1 Sustainability Impact

Flexible assignment, from an environmental perspective, may result in greater operational efficiency and lower resource and infrastructure consumption, indirectly reducing the environmental impact associated with process execution.

4.2.2 Flexible assignment Through a Sustainability Lens

This practice, viewed from a sustainability perspective, would have a greater impact in scenarios where the use of the most sustainable available resources is prioritized for task execution. For example, some tasks could be assigned based on the available infrastructure that is more efficient.

4.3 Centralization

This practice is based on “treating geographically dispersed resources as if they are centralized” through the use of workflow management systems. This enables the redistribution of tasks among resources located in different places, improving flexibility and potentially reducing the process throughput time.

4.3.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice may have effects that are highly dependent on the sustainability context. The possibility of assigning work among geographically distributed resources may improve the utilization of available resources, although it may also imply a greater use of technological infrastructure to support such coordination.

4.3.2 Centralization Through a Sustainability Lens

This practice becomes important when the impact associated with resources and tasks varies according to their geographical location. For example, the environmental impact generated by the energy consumption of an infrastructure may differ depending on the energy mix of each region. In these scenarios, work assignment could prioritize resources located in places where energy comes predominantly from renewable sources. There are countries such as Uruguay, where practically all electricity generation comes from renewable sources, meaning that certain tasks could be executed preferably on infrastructures located in these environments. Similarly, other factors could be considered, such as water availability, transport-related emissions, or the environmental efficiency of the infrastructure being used.

4.4 Split responsibilities

This practice aims to reduce the overlap of responsibilities by “avoiding the assignment of task responsibilities to people from different functional units.” It seeks to improve process quality and potentially reduce service times. However, it has been noted that reducing the number of resources capable of performing certain tasks may negatively affect throughput time.

4.4.1 Sustainability Impact

From a sustainability perspective, a lower number of information exchanges, authorization tasks, and rework activities may reduce the consumption associated with support activities and information systems, as well as waste generation, material usage, and related environmental impacts.

4.4.2 Split responsibilities Through a Sustainability Lens

This recommendation could be considered from a sustainability perspective to define explicit responsibilities regarding the environmental impacts associated with process tasks, for example, assigning tasks that has related sustainability objectives to the same department workers, so they can be aligned instead of splitted. In this way, it can improve aspects such as the monitoring and measurement of sustainability objectives.

4.5 Customer teams

This practice, which proposes to “consider assigning teams out of different departmental workers that will take care of the complete handling of specific sorts of orders,” is a variation of Order Assignment. In addition, it introduces teams composed of workers from different departments, providing greater capacity to handle specific types of orders.

4.5.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice may influence sustainability in different ways depending on how customer teams are organized. Similar to Order Assignment, dedicating specific teams to particular customers may reduce rework and errors, thereby decreasing the waste generation and resource consumption associated with process execution.

4.5.2 Customer teams Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, organizations should evaluate whether the composition of customer teams contributes to a more sustainable process execution. This practice would focus on selecting customer teams based on minimizing the sustainability impact of tasks for specific types of customers and providing them with this objective.

4.6 Numerical involvement

Numerical involvement aims to “minimize the number of departments, groups and persons involved in a business process,” thereby reducing the time and effort required for coordination among the departments, groups, and individuals involved in the process.

4.6.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice translates into a lower environmental impact from information transfers, as well as lower energy and material consumption associated with these activities. It also reduces the need for coordination activities and software integration and orchestration mechanisms between different systems and organizational actor, minimizing errors and associated rework, as well as materials use.

4.6.2 Numerical involvement Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, this practice could be favorable if the impact associated with each department is considered, for example, its geographical location. When prioritizing which departments could be minimized, this should be analyzed taking into account their sustainability-related aspects.

4.7 Case manager

The purpose of this best practice is to improve process quality by assigning a person responsible for each type of case: ‘appoint one person as responsible for the handling of each type of order, the case manager’. This may significantly affect costs, as it involves an overhead associated with management, controls,

monitoring, and potential rework. The most evident consequence of this heuristic in its original proposal is the improvement of the external quality of the process.

4.7.1 Sustainability Impact

This may have a positive impact on sustainability, since if there is a case manager, there is a single point of contact (which improves quality). Wasteful interactions are actually avoided in this way, there are less errors, and resource utilization is optimized.

4.7.2 Case manager Through a Sustainability Lens

The case manager practice refers here to appoint someone who will be managing the sustainable execution of the process for a particular case. This would not only improve sustainability outcomes but could also function as a mechanism to facilitate and encourage other actors to adopt these approaches.

4.8 Extra resources

This practice aims to improve processes through the addition of new resources. In particular, it proposes that “if capacity is not sufficient, consider increasing the number of resources.” This may provide greater operational capacity, reduce waiting times, and improve process performance. However, it may also negatively affect costs due to the need for additional resources.

4.8.1 Sustainability Impact

This best practice may enable a higher level of activity, potentially leading to increased energy consumption, emissions, material usage, and waste generation. The overall impact will depend on the type of resource added and on whether it reduces process inefficiencies or mainly adds capacity.

4.8.2 Extra resources Through a Sustainability Lens

This best practice is recommended in scenarios where incorporating new resources does not imply a considerable sustainability impact. For example, selecting tasks that, due to their nature, generate little or no waste and require little or no paper use, or when adding resources will not negatively impact energy consumption or CO₂ emissions.

4.9 Specialist-generalist

This practice seeks to determine the appropriate balance between specialists and generalists. Specialists typically provide higher quality and faster execution, while generalists offer greater flexibility and better resource utilization.

4.9.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice has two perspectives of analysis. From a sustainability perspective, having more specialist than generalist resources may have a positive impact, as specialists can reduce process execution time and improve the quality of the performed tasks. As a result, energy consumption, emissions, and waste generation may be reduced. Conversely, in the opposite scenario, the impact may be negative for the same reasons.

4.9.2 Specialist-generalist Through a Sustainability Lens

Resources can be more specialized on sustainability elements and objectives for the process, where specialization is based on sustainability training and interest, as opposed to generalist workers without sustainability awareness. It is also possible to consider hiring new resources with sustainability background, who can help in monitoring and maintaining the sustainability of the process.

4.10 Empower

Empower seeks to “give workers most of the decision-making authority and reduce middle management.” Granting workers greater autonomy can enable smoother operations and reduce throughput times. However, it may also negatively affect quality and increase costs if decisions are not made appropriately.

4.10.1 Sustainability Impact

The impact on sustainability would be positive, since fewer activities would be required from middle management, thus reducing energy consumption and potential waste generation or material use. However, as this practice may lead to rework due to undetected errors, its sustainability impact could also be negative for the opposite reason.

4.10.2 Empower Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, this practice is recommended in scenarios where workers have the capabilities and tools required to mitigate the impacts associated with their activities. However, this may be difficult to implement if there is a high degree of independence between different tasks, making it harder to achieve the coordination required to minimize resource, energy, and material consumption.

5 Information

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Information heuristics. Figure 6 shows the Devil’s Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 6: Devil’s pentagon for Information Heuristics

5.1 Control addition

In Control Addition, the aim is to ‘check the completeness and correctness of incoming materials and check the output before it is sent to customers’. This could improve quality and reduce costs because less rework is needed. On the other hand, adding controls may negatively impact the overall process time.

5.1.1 Sustainability Impact

The incorporation of additional controls may increase resource consumption due to extra validation and verification activities. In particular, it may negatively affect the impact associated with software when the controls require greater complexity in the processing logic, integration, or execution of systems. However, these controls may also reduce errors, rework, and waste. In Figure 4a the sustainability impact analysis on the Devil’s Pentagon is presented extended from [1], maintaining the original evaluation on the rest of the dimensions.

5.1.2 Control addition Through a Sustainability Lens

The addition of controls over the materials and products delivered to customers should be prioritized from a sustainability perspective. For example, controls could be incorporated to ensure the sustainable origin of the materials used in processes or to verify compliance with specific environmental criteria by suppliers and partners. This may imply a considerable improvement by reducing the environmental impacts associated with the supply chain and the final products.

5.2 Buffering

This practice aims to keep relevant information readily available when needed, reducing access times and improving throughput time, although it may increase storage and maintenance costs.

5.2.1 Sustainability Impact

The sustainability impact of this heuristic will be mostly positive due to the minimal impact of connecting systems and storage for receiving such information in a digital way.

5.2.2 Buffering Through a Sustainability Lens

This practice should be considered in systems with a high dependency on external parties. In addition, since information is accumulated and remains available, it can be processed in batches. These more demanding processing tasks could be scheduled to be performed at times when their impact is minimal.

6 Technology

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the Technology heuristics. Figure 7 shows the Devil's Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 7: Devil's pentagon for Technology Heuristics

6.1 Task automation

This practice proposes to 'consider automating tasks' in order to achieve faster process execution, reduce costs, and improve process results. The main disadvantage is that automating certain tasks may require a considerable investment, mostly at the moment of the original heuristic proposal.

6.1.1 Sustainability Impact

Task automation can have a favorable impact thanks to the reduction of overall process execution times and may also improve sustainability by reducing rework and optimizing the use of material resources, energy, and emissions. On the other hand, the reduction of operational costs and processing times may encourage an increase in process volume, which could result in a higher environmental impact. However, automation shifts the environmental impact toward the energy consumption of technological infrastructure and the hardware life cycle. For example, Agentic Business Process Management (BPM) could increase the energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, use of water.

6.1.2 Task automation Through a Sustainability Lens

Automation replaces human effort with digital systems, shifting the environmental impact toward the energy consumption of technological infrastructure and the hardware life cycle. The priority when automating tasks should be to automate those whose sustainability impact is greater than the impact generated by the automation itself. In particular, due to recent advances in generative artificial intelligence, the technical barrier to automating tasks has been reduced, with a direct implication in the use of LLMs and the infrastructure required for their execution. This considerably affects the environment

6.2 Integral technology

This heuristic seeks to incorporate technology to minimize physical constraints. An example is the use of specialized systems, such as Workflow Management Systems (WfMS). In addition, these technologies can improve information availability and reduce the time spent on various tasks. On the other hand, the acquisition, implementation, and maintenance of such systems may be costly.

6.2.1 Sustainability Impact

This practice aims to eliminate physical constraints through digital systems and new technology, facilitating the dematerialization of processes and directly reducing physical waste and emissions. This approach shifts the environmental burden toward technological infrastructure; this may represent an improvement in the overall impact of processes, but there is also a risk of worsening it. For example, the integration of agentic systems and generative AI may substantially optimize time and costs, but it involves high energy consumption, cooling systems, and the environmental impact associated with massive processing in data centers.

6.2.2 Integral technology Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, the incorporation of new technologies should prioritize situations where existing constraints generate significant environmental impacts and where their digitalization does not imply a greater overall impact. Technology can be used to eliminate or reduce activities with high resource consumption, improve the utilization of available infrastructure, or facilitate the monitoring and control of sustainability indicators.

7 External environment

This section presents the sustainability analysis of the external environment heuristics. Figure 8 shows the Devil's Pentagons for these heuristics.

Figure 8: Devil's pentagon for External Environment Heuristics

7.1 Trusted party

This practice seeks to reuse information or assessments performed by trusted third parties, avoiding the need to repeat activities within the process. This can reduce costs and execution times, although it creates a dependency on the quality of the information provided by third parties and may require additional coordination efforts.

7.1.1 Sustainability Impact

Reliable integrations within processes may provide opportunities to reduce controls and process tasks. In addition, they may encourage the standardization of exchanges, which also reduces rework activities and improves material consumption and waste generation.

7.1.2 Trusted party Through a Sustainability Lens

From a sustainability perspective, this practice may provide many benefits if exchanges are prioritized with external actors that possess verifiable sustainability certifications and validations. In this case, when adopting a global view of the process that goes beyond the interorganizational process itself, if the parties involved provide assurance that they respect the sustainability of their processes, it creates a favorable scenario in which the practices discussed above can be applied, particularly in situations where the potential problem was delegating responsibility for sustainability.

7.2 Outsourcing

This practice proposes to “consider outsourcing a business process in whole or parts of it,” that is, delegating processes or parts of them to third parties that can perform them more efficiently. This may reduce costs, although it can also affect quality and require greater coordination efforts between the parties involved.

7.2.1 Sustainability Impact

The direct impact is positive because the process ceases to be part of the organization, either totally or partially. All the impact associated with it could be considered to disappear. Similarly to what was discussed in Control Relocation, this may imply transferring the impact from one organization to another, meaning that, at a global level, the environmental impact would still exist.

7.2.2 Outsourcing Through a Sustainability Lens

Outsourcing would be recommended from a sustainability perspective when the process, or part of the process, is delegated to another organization that can ensure the process will be more sustainable. For example, production systems located in a country whose energy generation sources are green or renewable may be a better option than the same production system in countries that do not have this advantage. However, this may introduce problems associated with new tasks that need to be performed, such as transporting those products from one country to another.

7.3 Interfacing

In the practice, ‘consider a standardized interface with customers and partners’, communication problems are reduced, mainly improving process quality while also potentially having a positive impact on process time and costs.

7.3.1 Sustainability Impact

Standardizing communications through interfaces allows the process to be optimized by avoiding errors and associated rework. This generates a positive effect, as it reduces the consequences of these problems, such as waste generation, energy consumption, and associated emissions.

7.3.2 Interfacing Through a Sustainability Lens

This practice may improve process sustainability by avoiding redundant information exchanges and additional processing in software systems, contributing to a more sustainable process execution. Likewise, the standardization of interfaces may reduce the need for specific or dedicated software solutions for each system integration. In addition, standardized interfaces may facilitate the exchange of sustainability data between organizations, enabling greater transparency and supporting the measurement and management of sustainability impacts throughout the process ecosystem.